

DOMESTIC WASTE MANAGEMENT AND COVID-19 PANDEMIC IN RIVERS STATE

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Abstract

The challenge posed by COVID-19 on poor waste management system in Rivers State calls for concern. Hence, the study investigated the management of solid waste in COVID-19 pandemic. A self structured questionnaire was administered to 256 households/respondents and data recovered were analyzed statistically and presented in percentages. Results on type of waste generated revealed food debris, bottles, ashes, cans, nylon and sanitary wastes had 93%, 75%, 82%, 80.5%, 75.8% and 1.2% positive responses respectively, while the respondents' disposal methods were: open dumping (99.2%), burying (43.4%), land filling (40.2%) and burning (60.5%). Other disposal methods employed are: composting and incineration methods with a disposal percentage of 0.8% and 0.0% respectively. Disposal of waste in bushes and river were noted 88.7% and 39.1% respectively. The high food wastage indicates environmental pollution and health risk and thus, open burning and throwing of waste inside bushes releases toxin into the environment which could encourage secondary transmission of diseases to human. The study concludes that COVID-19 should be an early warning signal for prompt measure on waste management for a healthy environment. Hence, households should ensure they follow emission requirements, so as to avoid secondary health impacts.